

To Study Of Value's Of Girls in Senior College

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Abstract:

The study was conducted to assess the values of T.Y.B.A. & T.Y.B.Com Girls Students. The sample consisted of total 60 girls, 30 girls in T.Y.B.A. faculty and 30 girls in T.Y.B.Com faculty were selected from S.S.C. College Junnar, Dist: Pune. The participants was last year undergraduate girls students. Simple random sampling method for used for data collection. For this study the value test developed by Kamal Dwivedi and Shagufta Hafeez, Kanpur was used to assess the values of the selected respondent. Mean, SD, 't' value etc. statistics techniques were used for data analysis and interpreting. The findings were no significant difference in the Aesthetic value of B.A. and B.Com girls in senior college, no significant difference in the Economic value of B.A. and B.Com girls in senior college, no significant difference in the Moral value of B.A. and B.Com girls in senior college, no significant difference in the Political value of B.A. and B.Com girls in senior college, no significant difference in the Religious value of B.A. and B.Com girls in senior college, no significant difference in the Social value of B.A. and B.Com girls in senior college and significant difference in the Theoretical value of B.A. and B.Com girls in senior college. This means, the Aesthetic, Economic, Moral, Political, Religious and Social value of B.A. and B.Com girls in senior college are similar. The Theoretical value of B.Com girls is higher than that of B.A. girls in senior college.

Introduction:

Values are difficult to study and persistent questions arise as to whether they are 'real', whether they actually can be shown to have causal influence on behavior. Everyday life is cast in terms of values and think of ethics, law, religion, politics, art, child rearing and more. Abstract value judgments are embodied in seeming gut reactions that something is right, moral, or natural vs. Wrong, immoral or unnatural. Another way to 'see' values in action is to contrast cultures or subcultures in what seems right, natural or moral.

Value means implicitly or explicitly we evaluate or assign value to everything regarding things as good or bad, a truth or falsity, a virtue or a vice. One important means is values can be thought of as priorities, internal compasses or springboards for action-moral imperatives. In this way, values or mores are implicit or explicit guides for action, general a script framing what is sought after and what is to be avoided. Values is a respect of a motivational which is referable to standard personal or cultural that does not arise solely out fo immediate tension. In psychology, value theory refers to the study of the manner in which human beings develop, assert and believe in certain values, and act or fail to act to them. Values are valuable in life which includes social, political, aesthetic, religious, moral, economical, and theoretical.

Spranger (1928) - Claasifies values adopted by population in the society into six major types. Theoretical Value - The primary value of the ideal theoretical man is the discovery of the truth.it involves the use of rational, critical, empirical processes. Such people are intellectual, research oriented and philosophical in nature.

a) Economical Value - In economics the net worth of thing is determined by what it will bring in exchange either in goods or in some medium of exchange usually money. Such types of people are money minded in nature.

b) Aesthetic Value - Aesthetic man has affection and great love for art and beauty. According to him/them economical and theoretical man are destructive of aesthetic values.

c) Social Value - It is also known as human value. Social man is one who ever, tries to understand the human values of truth, right conduct, peace, love and non-violence properly the one who practices these values and propagates them with zeal and sincerity can alone be described as truly socially educated person.

d) Political Value - It is also known as a 'power value' such type of person always busy in expansion and maintenance of his position and power in society and for sake of this they can do any thing without thinking or evaluating its moral value.

e) Religious Value - It is also known as philosophical value. Such higher value based people dedicate their whole life for society. He cultivates love for all which leads to 'Unity' and that's promotes divinity.

Rationale of study:

Considering both the above T.Y.B.A. & T.Y.B.Com girls students faculty and syllabus is different. Their job and business opportunities are different in their future. Does this factor cause the values of these students to be different? And the purpose of this study is to be know their attitude towards life.

Objective of Study:

To study the values of girls in senior college.

Hypothesis:

1. There is no significant difference in the Aesthetic value of B.A. and B.Com girls in senior college.
2. There is no significant difference in the Economic value of B.A. and B.Com girls in senior college.
3. There is no significant difference in the Moral value of B.A. and B.Com girls in senior college.
4. There is no significant difference in the Political value of B.A. and B.Com girls in senior college.
5. There is no significant difference in the Religious value of B.A. and B.Com girls in senior college.
6. There is no significant difference in the Social value of B.A. and B.Com girls in senior college.
7. There is no significant difference in the Theoretical value of B.A. and B.Com girls in senior college.

Method:

1. **Sample:** In this study, researcher has select total 60 girls students in senior college, 30 girls

in T.Y.B.A. class and 30 girls in T.Y.B.Com class. Sample was select from S.S.C.College Junnar, Dist: Pune through simple random sampling method for used for data collection. The participants was last year undergraduate girls students.

2. **Variable:** Independent Variable:- T.Y.B.A. and T.Y.B.Com Girls. Dependent Variable:- Values
3. **Research Tools:** The Value Test developed by Kamal Dwivedi and Shagufta Hafeez, Kanpur. This test consists of seven values i.e. Aesthetic, Economics, Moral, Political, Religious, Social and Theoretical etc. There are eight groups and each group having seven items. Validity and Reliability: Discriminative power of the items has been used as the criterion of validity and internal consistency of items is that of reliability.
4. **Statistical Analysis:** In the present research Mean, SD, 't' value etc. Statistical techniques were used for the data analysis and interpretation.

Result & Discussion:

Table No. 1 showing the significant difference in aesthetic value of B.A. & B.com Girls.

Variable	Type	Mean	SD	N	't'	Sign.
Aesthetic value	T.Y.B.A. Girls	31.33	5.20	30	0.75	NS
	T.Y.B.Com Girls	30.17	6.66	30		

The table no. 1 it is shows that, the T.Y.B.A.girls mean value is 31.33 and standard deviation value is 5.20. Like the T.Y.B.Com girls mean value is 30.17 and standard deviation value is 6.66. The T.Y.B.A.Girls mean value is more than T.Y.B.Com girls. Obtained 't' value of the difference between

the mean of these two groups was found to be 0.75. This is no significant at 0.05 levels. So the null hypothesis was accepted. That is, there was a no significant difference of aesthetic value of B.A. & B.com Girls.

Table No. 2 showing the significant difference in economics value of B.A. & B.com Girls.

Variable	Type	Mean	SD	N	't'	Sign.
Economics value	T.Y.B.A. Girls	32.67	4.99	30	0.85	.S
	T.Y.B.Com Girls	33.83	5.64	30		

The table no. 2 it is shows that, the T.Y.B.A.girls mean value is 32.67 and standard deviation value is 4.99. Like the T.Y.B.Com girls mean value is 33.83 and standard deviation value is 5.64. The T.Y.B.Com girls mean value is more than T.Y.B.A.

girls. Obtained 't' value of the difference between the mean of these two groups was found to be 0.85. This is no significant at 0.05 levels. So the null hypothesis was accepted. That is, there was a no significant difference of economics value of B.A. & B.com Girls.

Table No. 3 showing the significant difference in moral value of B.A. & B.com Girls.

Variable	Type	Mean	SD	N	't'	Sign.
Moral value	T.Y.B.A. Girls	29.67	4.99	30	1.56	NS
	T.Y.B.Com Girls	27.5	5.64	30		

The table no. 3 it is shows that, the T.Y.B.A.girls mean value is 29.67 and standard deviation value is 4.99. Like the T.Y.B.Com girls mean value is 27.5 and standard deviation value is 5.64. The T.Y.B.A.girls mean value is more than T.Y.B.Com girls. Obtained 't' value of the difference between

the mean of these two groups was found to be 1.56. This is no significant at 0.05 levels. So the null hypothesis was accepted. That is, there was a no significant difference of moral value of B.A. & B.com Girls.

Table No. 4 showing the significant difference in political value of B.A. & B.com Girls.

Variable	Type	Mean	SD	N	't'	Sign.
Political value	T.Y.B.A. Girls	30.83	5.11	30	0.92	NS
	T.Y.B.Com Girls	32.17	6.06	30		

The table no. 4 it is shows that, the T.Y.B.A. girls mean value is 30.83 and standard deviation value is 5.11. Like the T.Y.B.Com girls mean value is 32.17 and standard deviation value is 6.06. The T.Y.B.Com girls mean value is more than T.Y.B.A girls. Obtained 't' value of the difference between

the mean of these two groups was found to be 0.92. This is no significant at 0.05 levels. So the null hypothesis was accepted. That is, there was a no significant difference of political value of B.A. & B.com Girls.

Table No. 5 showing the significant difference in religious value of B.A. & B.com Girls.

Variable	Type	Mean	SD	N	't'	Sign.
Religious Value	T.Y.B.A. Girls	36	5.85	30	0.24	NS
	T.Y.B.Com Girls	36.33	4.87	30		

The table no. 5 it is shows that, the T.Y.B.A. girls mean value is 36 and standard deviation value is 5.85. Like the T.Y.B.Com girls mean value is 36.33 and standard deviation value is 4.87. The T.Y.B.Com girls mean value is more than T.Y.B.A girls. Obtained 't' value of the difference between

the mean of these two groups was found to be 0.24. This is no significant at 0.05 levels. So the null hypothesis was accepted. That is, there was a no significant difference of religious value of B.A. & B.com Girls.

Table No. 6 showing the significant difference in social value of B.A. & B.com Girls.

Variable	Type	Mean	SD	N	't'	Sign.
Social value	T.Y.B.A. Girls	31.83	5.12	30	0.48	NS
	T.Y.B.Com Girls	32.5	5.67	30		

The table no. 6 it is shows that, the T.Y.B.A. girls mean value is 31.83 and standard deviation value is 5.12. Like the T.Y.B.Com girls mean value is 32.5 and standard deviation value is 5.67. The T.Y.B.Com girls mean value is more than T.Y.B.A girls. Obtained 't' value of the difference between

the mean of these two groups was found to be 0.48. This is no significant at 0.05 levels. So the null hypothesis was accepted. That is, there was a no significant difference of social value of B.A. & B.com Girls.

Table No. 7 showing the significant difference in theoretical value of B.A. & B.com Girls.

Variable	Type	Mean	SD	N	't'	Sign.
Theoretical value	T.Y.B.A. Girls	28	5.32	30	3.00	0.05
	T.Y.B.Com Girls	32.5	6.25	30		

The table no. 7 it is shows that, the T.Y.B.A. girls mean value is 28 and standard deviation value is 5.32. Like the T.Y.B.Com girls mean value is 32.5 and standard deviation value is 6.25. The T.Y.B.Com girls mean value is more than T.Y.B.A. girls. Obtained 't' value of the difference between the mean of these two groups was found to be 3.00. This is significant at 0.05 levels. So the null hypothesis was rejected. That is, there was a significant difference of theoretical value of B.A. & B.com Girls.

Conclusion:

There is no significant difference in the Aesthetic value of B.A. and B.Com girls in senior college, no significant difference in the Economic value of B.A. and B.Com girls in senior college, no significant difference in the Moral value of B.A. and B.Com girls in senior college, no significant difference in the Political value of B.A. and B.Com girls in senior college, no significant difference in the Religious value of B.A. and B.Com girls in senior college, no significant difference in the Social value of B.A. and B.Com girls in senior college and significant difference in the Theoretical value of B.A. and B.Com girls in senior college. This means, the Aesthetic, Economic, Moral, Political, Religious and Social value of B.A. and B.Com girls in senior college are similar. The Theoretical value of B.Com girls is higher than that of B.A. girls in senior college.

Suggestions:

1. A large number of samples can be taken in future research.
2. The study area for further research will come from a wide area.
3. Various techniques should be used to analyze the scores.

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